

THE DARK TRIAD PERSONALITY TRAITS AND EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: UNVEILING THE HIDDEN INFLUENCES IN THE WORKPLACE

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ABSTRACT

This quantitative study investigates the relationship between Dark Triad personality traits (Machiavellianism, Narcissism, and Psychopathy) and work performance among working adults in Pakistan. A cross-sectional survey design was employed, with a sample (N=300) participant from diverse organizational sectors. Results showed that Machiavellianism emerged as a significant predictor of work performance. Narcissism also significantly predicts work performance. Whereas psychopathy does not predict job crafting. Additionally, the study found significant gender differences in work performance, but no differences in Dark Triad personality traits across genders. This study contributes to our understanding of the Dark Triad personality traits in a non-Western cultural context, highlighting the importance of considering cultural nuances in organizational behavior. The findings have implications for clinicians, organizations, and human resource practitioners, providing insights into the recruitment, screening, and development of employees with Dark Triad personality traits. By understanding the unique characteristics and strengths of these individuals, organizations can leverage their talents to achieve better outcomes, while clinicians can develop more effective interventions to support their personal and professional growth. Limitations and future directions are discussed, highlighting the need for longitudinal and experimental studies to further explore the relationships between Dark Triad personality traits, and work outcomes such as job crafting, and work performance, turnover rates and many more.

Keywords: Dark triad personality traits, Narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy, Work Performance.

INTRODUCTION

The "Dark Triad" refers to a set of three maladaptive personality traits—Machiavellianism, narcissism, and psychopathy—that individuals may exhibit in both social and professional settings (Volmer et al., 2016). These traits, characterized by manipulation, self-centeredness, and a lack of empathy, can significantly influence workplace dynamics, affecting how employees

interact with one another. Personality traits are fundamental, enduring tendencies that shape individuals' behavior across various contexts. In organizational settings, the presence of Dark Triad traits can have detrimental effects, as these characteristics are linked to unethical conduct and destructive behavior. Research has shown that individuals high in these traits are more

prone to engage in dishonest or illicit activities, such as theft (Forsyth et al., 2012). Furthermore, their toxic behaviors can create a hostile work environment, potentially driving away committed employees who seek a more supportive and constructive atmosphere (LeBreton et al., 2018). The concept of the Dark Triad was first introduced by Paulhus and Williams (2002), who described these personality traits as existing along a continuum of typical behavior but marked by egocentrism, emotional coldness, and manipulation. These individuals often display rude, arrogant, and harmful behaviors when interacting with others. Despite the recognition of these traits, there remains no consensus on a unified conceptualization of the Dark Triad, owing to its complex and evolving nature (Schreiber & Marcus, 2020). One significant disadvantage of Machiavellianism is the tendency of individuals with this trait to seek revenge and deceive even those they value to achieve their personal desires (Forsyth et al., 2012). In organizational settings, individuals displaying Machiavellian tendencies prioritize their self-interest and financial gain over the goals of the organization. This often leads to unethical behaviors, such as engaging in dishonest practices, exploiting colleagues for personal advancement, and dismissing coworkers for self-serving reasons (LeBreton et al., 2018). Psychopathy, on the other hand, is associated with a broader range of criminal activities, including sexual assault and murder (Megargee, 2009). Psychopaths often manipulate testing and interview processes using deceitful tactics to secure positions within organizations, relying on false charm to achieve their objectives (Khan et al., 2020). When individuals with psychopathic traits assume leadership roles, their manipulative behaviors can create a toxic work environment marked by fear, intimidation, and a focus on personal gain at the expense of organizational interests. These individuals disrupt team dynamics by undermining collaboration, communication, and trust, contributing to an antagonistic workplace. The negative impact on employees' emotional well-being and physical health is compounded by a lack of accountability and empathy within such an environment (Baka, 2019). Forsyth et al. (2012) further note that the presence of psychopathy is negatively correlated with Machiavellianism and overall work

performance, with an increase in psychopathic traits linked to a rise in unproductive office behaviors. Additionally, studies indicate that workplace bullying by controlling managers stifles employee creativity and reduces organizational efficiency and innovation (Khan et al., 2020). In contrast, narcissism is often associated with high levels of self-perceived creativity and confidence. Research has shown that individuals with narcissistic traits may exhibit a strong belief in their unique ideas, motivating them to take risks to pursue their creative ambitions (Jonason et al., 2012).

Machiavellianism, however, tends to prioritize personal gain over collective innovation and originality. Individuals exhibiting Machiavellian traits are often focused on manipulating situations or undermining the contributions of others to further their own interests. This behavior can hinder the development of positive traits such as creativity, leadership potential, and career dedication (Zettler et al., 2011). Consequently, such actions obstruct the free exchange of ideas, exploration of diverse viewpoints, and the overall cultivation of innovative solutions.

On the other hand, recent research highlights that it is crucial to also consider the potential positive aspects of the Dark Triad traits. Studies have shown that these traits are frequently associated with characteristics linked to professional success and leadership, such as job satisfaction, rapid career advancement, and higher salaries (AL-Abrow et al., 2020; Volmer et al., 2016). Creativity, for instance, has been associated with the ability to generate, disseminate, and implement novel ideas. Even when considered independently, the components of the Dark Triad may offer benefits. Narcissism, for example, is linked to traits such as boldness, individuality, and a desire to challenge conventions, which can foster the emergence of dynamic leaders (AL-Abrow et al., 2020). Narcissistic individuals are often highly innovative and persuasive within business settings. Similarly, psychopathy has been found to correlate positively with traits such as charisma and effective presentation skills (Babiak et al., 2010). Moreover, Machiavellianism is often associated with a strong commitment to work and an ability to drive professional outcomes.

In conclusion, while the Dark Triad traits can present both advantages and disadvantages, they often result in a prioritization of personal goals over collective objectives. Narcissistic individuals, for instance, may dominate conversations and demand attention in communication, while psychopaths, due to their lack of empathy, struggle to understand the perspectives and social dynamics of others. According to LeBreton et al. (2018), when multiple individuals with psychopathic traits are present in a team, it can lead to reduced cohesion, lower commitment, and diminished team performance. Psychopaths, driven by a desire for dominance and aggression, tend to lack a sense of community and constructive collaboration.

Workplace motivation is closely tied to organizational goals such as job satisfaction, commitment, and strong organizational identity. As Peak (1955) asserts, "motivation and attitude are highly interdependent and closely related" (p. 149). The cycle of high performance in organizations often includes dedication, job fulfillment, and strong work motivation (Locke & Latham, 1990). However, it is important to recognize that work motivation is a complex phenomenon with multiple underlying causes. Job motivation and work attitude are distinct constructs; an individual may be highly motivated yet possess a negative outlook at work, or vice versa. Work motivation refers to the internal and external factors that influence work-related behaviors, while workplace attitudes are characterized by satisfaction, commitment, and organizational identification (Lohela-Karlsson et al., 2022).

Hypotheses

1. Narcissism is a significant predictor of task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive work behavior among working adults.
2. Machiavellianism is a significant predictor of task performance and counterproductive work behavior among working adults.
3. Machiavellianism is not a significant predictor of contextual performance among working adults.
4. Psychopathy is a significant predictor of counterproductive work behavior among working adults.

5. Psychopathy is not a significant predictor of task performance and contextual performance among working adults.

6. Narcissism and Machiavellianism is a significant predictors of individual work performance among working adults.

7. Working adult's male are better in work performance than working adults' female.

Work performance

Recent shifts in occupational health research have primarily focused on preventing productivity loss due to illness or disability. In contrast, the field of management has largely concentrated on strategies to maximize employee productivity (Koopmans et al., 2014). On the other hand, work and organizational psychologists explore the impact of factors such as personality, work engagement, and job satisfaction on individual performance (Koopmans et al., 2009). An essential objective measure commonly used in occupational settings across various domains is individual job efficiency. However, despite its importance, there remains a lack of a comprehensive conceptual framework for understanding individual work performance. To ensure optimal measurement, a solid theoretical foundation is crucial.

In the construction industry, time constraints are among the most significant challenges (Memon et al., 2023). Addressing these challenges often hinges on employee performance. According to Ahmad and Shahzad (2011), an employee's perceived accomplishments reflect their belief in the value of their contributions toward achieving the organization's vision and goals. The authors further emphasize that employee performance is indicated by factors such as career development programs, performance reviews, and compensation practices. For construction site personnel, employee performance is particularly critical to the success of projects (Prasetya, Natalia & Stella, 2020).

Job safety and security also represent crucial workplace concerns that must be effectively addressed to provide employees with a secure and adaptable working environment. The well-being of employees is intrinsically linked to the overall productivity of a company. When employees feel secure, they tend to operate in a more positive environment, which enables better focus and greater productivity. Previous research has

demonstrated a direct correlation between job satisfaction and factors such as salary, psychological autonomy, compensation, medical benefits, workplace stress, and working conditions.

Wallace and Baumeister's (2002) theory posit that narcissists, driven by a desire for self-improvement, are more likely to exert greater effort when they believe opportunities for fame are within reach. Conversely, they will invest less effort when they perceive such opportunities to be absent. These authors suggest that variations in effort may mediate the relationship between narcissism and performance outcomes. Although this theoretical framework is plausible, the connection between effort and narcissistic performance has only been explored in one study. Woodman et al. (2011) conducted an experiment where participants in a cycling task were asked to ride as far as possible for ten minutes under two conditions: one where their performance could be recognized and another where it could not. The results showed that narcissists cycled more than a kilometer farther when their performance was acknowledged, and this increase in effort was reflected in improvements in aerobic capacity, such as heart rate and perceived effort. While this study demonstrates a correlation between effort and performance, it does not conclusively establish that effort is the causal factor behind performance gains under pressure. Moreover, as many tasks involve both physical and mental exertion, it remains unclear how these two aspects of effort interact to affect narcissists' performance.

In contrast, research has shown a weak negative correlation between Machiavellian traits and job performance. Instead, these traits are more strongly associated with maladaptive behaviors in the workplace (Forsyth et al., 2012). Interestingly, under certain conditions—such as when resources are scarce, Machiavellianism has been linked to improved performance, despite its generally negative association with work outcomes (Kuyumcu & Dahling, 2014). However, given the limited research on this topic, the relationship between Machiavellianism and performance remains underexplored (Jones & Paulhus, 2009), and scholars have called for further investigation into the mediating mechanisms at play (Harms et al., 2011; Spain et al., 2014). O'Boyle et al. (2012)

found a negative correlation between Machiavellianism and work quality, alongside an increase in psychopathy. They also observed a rise in ineffective office behaviors. Workplace bullying by dominant supervisors has been shown to reduce organizational efficiency, stifle creativity, and diminish innovation (Khan et al., 2020). Psychopaths, whose antisocial tendencies hinder their creativity, may struggle to share their accomplishments and ideas with others (Steinert et al., 2017). Their lack of self-control and recklessness may further impede their ability to meet intellectual demands, as they become excessively focused on success at the expense of productive collaboration (Khan et al., 2020). In contrast, narcissism has been linked to higher levels of self-perceived creativity and confidence in one's abilities, potentially enhancing an individual's belief in their capacity for innovative thinking.

Socio analytic theory (Hogan & Blicke, 2013) can be used to better understand the implications of Machiavellianism for job performance. This theory proposes that reputation specifically mediates the relationship between personality and performance, and that social competence balances the association between reputation and personality (Hogan & Shelton, 1998). According to Hochwarter et al. (2007), social skill transforms personality into acts that are noticed by others and assessed as having a positive reputation. To Machiavellianism in the workplace, higher levels of political skill—or work social skill—assist Machiavellians in selecting more effective social strategies, such as controlling their antagonistic impulses and concealing their intents from others (Waldman et al., 2018). Therefore, improved Machiavellian job results are produced by enhanced political skill that masks their manipulative techniques (Blickle et al., 2020).

The cause of the current spike in curiosity around the alleged "corporate psychopath", that demonstrates many of the characteristics of psychopathy, yet does not reach the point of acting in an antisocial or illegal manner which could end up in a record of crimes, is the worry that these individuals are causing harm to workers, their organizations, the economy, and the environment (Babiak, 1995). Early definitions of psychopathy often included this

illegal behavior as one of its defining characteristics, but more recently, the term has come to refer to a pathological condition in which persistently aberrant activity is combined with emotional detachment (Patrick et al., 2009). There have been suggestions that some people can make use of their own psychotic traits adaptively in the workplace due to knowledge that Psychopathy usually entails aberrant behavior, though not necessarily (Somma et al., 2019). It was acknowledged that psychopathy-related qualities might be advantageous in the workplace for several reasons. First off, charisma and confidence are two traits of psychopathy that are advantageous in the social setting of the workplace (Boddy, 2015). Second, brave and fearless leaders can benefit the organization as well as their followers (Smith & Lilienfeld, 2013). Third, there are some professions, like the military or law enforcement, where some psychopathy-related qualities, such fearlessness and low stress reactivity, may be highly advantageous (Falkenbach, Glackin & McKinley, 2018).

Materials and methodology

The study's non-probability convenient sample consists of 300 working people from Islamabad's public and private sectors. Banks and other financial organizations, business sectors, and service industries are types of organizations from where the data is collected. Both males and females are a part of study. Their educational background ranges from matriculation to PhDs. Participants had to have been employed for at least a year to guarantee that they had had the chance to perform well in their positions, have a sufficient command of English. This criterion was set in accordance with the inclusion criteria of a research done by Geldenhuys, Bakker and Demerouti (2020).

Measures

Demographics

A thorough demographic sheet was created after a variety of demographics were observed to gather data. Demographics included detailed information about the participant's gender, age, family structure, education, work experience, occupation, and monthly income.

Table 1: Frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables of the study (N=300)

Variable	f	%
Gender		
Male	183	39
Female	117	61
Education		
FSC	28	9.3
Graduate	162	54
Masters	107	35.6
PhD	3	1
Employment experience		
1 to 3 years	121	40.3
4 to 6 years	67	22.3
7 to 9 years	28	9.3
Above 10 years	84	28
Marital Status		
Single	144	48
Married	154	51.3
Divorced	3	1
Illness		
Yes	11	3.6
No	289	96.3
Age	Mean=30.14	SD=7.54

Note: f= frequency, %= Percentage

Dark triad personality traits

The Dirty Dozen, a measure of the Dark Triad (narcissism, psychopathy, and Machiavellianism; Paulhus & Williams, 2002), a 12-item scale, was proposed by Jonason and Webster (2010). Each of the three qualities is measured briefly using four items for each dimension. To rate each scale, add the corresponding elements on an ordinal 7-point scale (strongly disagree = 1, strongly agree = 7). The Machiavellianism, Psychopathy, and Narcissism subscales had mean item-level temporal reliability of .92, .84, and .92, respectively.

Work performance

Work performance of an employee is based on many factors but three main and significant dimensions which are task performance, contextual performance and counterproductive behavior has been identified by many researchers. While task performance is described as acts that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the company's technical foundation must operate, contextual performance refers to operations that either positively or negatively assist the technological core of the organization (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). Contextual performance is the collective term for individual acts that maintain the organizational, social, and psychological environment necessary for the technical foundation to function (Borman & Motowidlo, 1993). The term "counterproductive work behavior" (CWB) refers to actions that put the organization's health in danger. It covers actions like not showing up for work on time, slacking off, stealing, and abusing drugs (Rotundo & Sackett 2022). All these constructions have been assessed on a single scale consisting of 18 items. Items 1-5 reflect task performance, 6-13 reflect contextual performance, 14-18 reflect counterproductive work behavior. The mean score for each IWPQ scale may be found by adding together all the item scores and dividing the result by the total number of items in the scale.

Procedure

The study used a quantitative method with a correlational research design to investigate the relationship between the variables. A convenience sampling strategy was applied to

examine the relationship between the variables. To enable the researchers to formulate predictions based on the correlations found, the study also sought to examine the direction and strength of the association between these factors. A sample of three hundred working adults from different organizations in Islamabad participated in the study. First and foremost, the organization's approval was obtained. The data was gathered with the participants' consent. They were informed of the study's goal. Additionally, they were informed about their freedom to decline and exit at any time. Instructions on how to fill out the questionnaire were also given to the participants. Furthermore, participants were informed that they could ask any questions they had without hesitation. The participants were likely to provide the proper response if they were given any questions pertaining to the topic. They were assured that any information they submitted would be kept confidential and used only for research purposes. The demographic data, which included information on age, gender, marital status, occupation, and educational background, were also collected in conjunction with the questionnaire. Every additional ethical guideline supplied by the American Psychological Association was adhered to. At the conclusion of data collection, each participant received a thank-you for their participation. After all the data were gathered, it was loaded into SPSS-21 and JASP-19 for further analysis and conclusion.

Statistical analysis

IBM SPSS Statistics, version 28.0.1.0, was used to conduct statistical analyses in a step-by-step manner. Prior to obtaining measures for central tendency and distribution, standardized (*Z*) scores were computed to check research variables for outliers. Second, to examine differences between male and female participants, independent sample tests were conducted. Regression analysis was conducted to predict work performance among working adults.

Results

Preliminary results

Regression analysis was conducted to predict the significance of predictors (Narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy) in task performance. Shown in table 2, Narcissism ($\beta = .111, p = .044$), Psychopathy ($\beta = -.120, p = .044$),

and Machiavellianism ($\beta = -.370, p = .000$), significantly predicts task performance.

Table 2: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Task performance (N=300)

Predictor	b	SE	β	t	p	95% CI	
						LL	UL
(Constant)	21.567	.616		35.031	.000	20.355	22.779
Narcissism	.066	.033	.111	2.026	.044	.002	.130
Machiavellianism	-.335	.056	-.370	-6.031	.000	-.445	-.226
Psychopathy	-.087	.043	-.120	-2.020	.044	-.172	-.002
R	.422 ^a						
R ²	.178						
ΔR^2	.170						
F	21.394						

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Regression analysis was conducted to predict the significance of predictors (Narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy) in contextual performance. Shown in table 3, Narcissism ($\beta =$

.147, $p = .012$), and Machiavellianism ($\beta = -.308$, $p = .000$), significantly predicts contextual performance. While Psychopathy ($\beta = -.005$, $p = .941$), does not predict contextual performance.

Table 3: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of Contextual Performance (N=300)

Predictor	b	SE	β	t	p	95% CI	
						LL	UL
(Constant)	31.571	1.063		29.688	.000	29.479	33.664
Narcissism	.143	.056	.147	2.538	.012	.032	.254
Machiavellianism	-.459	.096	-.308	-4.772	.000	-.648	-.269
Psychopathy	-.006	.075	-.005	-.074	.941	-.152	.141
R	.303 ^a						
R ²	.092						
ΔR^2	.083						
F	9.987						

Note. * $p < .05$, ** $p < .01$, *** $p < .001$

Regression analysis was conducted to predict the significance of predictors (Narcissism, Machiavellianism, psychopathy) in counterproductive work behavior. Shown in

table 4, Machiavellianism ($\beta = .275$, $p = .000$), and Psychopathy ($\beta = .145$, $p = .017$), significantly predict counterproductive work behavior. While Narcissism ($\beta = .091$, $p = .102$), does not predict counterproductive work behavior.

Table 4: Multiple Regression Analysis of Predictors of counterproductive work behavior (N=300)

Predictor	b	SE	β	t	p	95% CI	
						LL	UL
(Constant)	5.988	.656		9.123	.000	4.696	7.280
Narcissism	.057	.035	.091	1.638	.102	-.011	.125
Machiavellianism	.263	.059	.275	4.435	.000	.146	.380
Psychopathy	.111	.046	.145	2.411	.017	.020	.202
R	.401 ^a						
R ²	.161						
ΔR^2	.152						

F	18.928						
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Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001

Results in Table 10 indicate differences among the male and female research participants.

Results documented lower, IWP and MAW among female participants as compared to male participants with a significant difference.

Table 10: Mean Differences in Predictor and Outcome Variable of Participants' Gender (N=300)

Variables	Male (n=183)		Female (n=117)		t	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Narcissism	14.71	7.097	15.09	6.212	-.474	.636
Machiavellianism	7.66	4.229	8.66	4.696	-1.908	.057
Psychopathy	9.62	5.368	10.83	5.767	-1.853	.065
IWP	111.97	19.102	101.60	18.103	4.675	.000
MAW	101.47	27.207	87.94	20.839	4.582	.000

Note. *p < .05, ** p < .01, ***p < .001, IWP–Individual work performance, MAW–Motivation at work

Discussion

One of the study's key findings is that participants with Machiavellian and Narcissistic personality traits do better at work than those with psychopath traits. Machiavelli argued in *The Prince* (1513/1981) that leaders who could disregard their morals and principles would succeed more than those who governed with integrity and honesty. These days, those who exhibit a disregard for traditional morality, emotional detachment, and a propensity to manipulate others are considered to possess high degrees of Machiavellian personality traits (Christie & Geis, 1970).

Following early research by Christie and Geis (1970: 312) that produced a personality construct with three dimensions—(a) support for deceit and manipulation, (b) a cynical view of human nature, and (c) a disregard for conventional morality—the study of Machiavellianism flourished in the 1970s. High Machs (workers with high levels of Machiavellianism) "manipulate more, win more, are persuaded less, persuade others more, and otherwise differ significantly from their low Machiavellian counterparts," according to Christie and Geis' research. Important distinctions between high Machs and low Machs (those with low levels of Machiavellianism) have been identified by subsequent research.

In addition to interpersonal coldness (Wiggins & Broughton, 1985), narcissism (McHoskey, 1995), anxiety (Fehr, Samsom, & Paulhus, 1992), and external locus of control (Mudrack, 1990), high

Machs are also more likely to be egocentric, cynical, distrustful, and prone to manipulating others (McHoskey, 1999).

Machiavellianism's purported connection to job performance sparked academics' interest in the field of management. According to Machiavelli's logic and the results of early research on Machiavellianism, academics have theorized that workers with high Machiavellianism should perform better at work than those with low Machs because they are more likely to manipulate (Christie & Geis, 1970; Wilson, Near, & Miller, 1996), lack empathy (Paal & Bereczkei, 2007), favor opportunism over cooperation (Sakalaki, Richardson, & Thepaut, 2007), seek retribution (Meyer, 1992), and are less likely to return favors. Thirty years of research, however, have produced conflicting findings. While some studies have found a positive relationship between Machiavellianism and work performance (Dahling, Whitaker, & Levy, 2009; Turner & Martinez, 1977), others have found a negative relationship (Gable & Topol, 1988; Topol & Gable, 1990), and still others have found no relationship at all (Gable & Topol, 1991; Gemmill & Heisler, 1972; Hunt & Chonko, 1984).

One of the study's other main conclusions is that workers with Machiavellian characteristics are more motivated, and motivated workers perform better at work. In contrast to narcissists and psychopaths, Machiavellians are very practical and logical leaders who lack a grand vision (Bedell et al., 2006: Christie and Geis, 1970:

Glad, 2002), despite their attitude (Gunnthorsdottir et al., 2002; Rauthmann, 2012). Their self-beneficial goal pursuit and agentic motives (such as money and power) are the foundation of their strategic long-term planning (Diehl et al., 2006; Elias, 2013; Fehr et al., 1992; Jones and Paulhus, 2009; Rauthmann and Will, 2011).

These behavioral patterns support exploration, innovation, and the pursuit of opportunities. Machiavellians are therefore less inclined to explore new areas. This is supported by their pursuit of unwavering success and winning at all costs (Ryckman et al., 1994). Furthermore, their strong focus on results only helps them achieve their own objectives (Fehr et al., 1992). According to Zettler et al. (2011), Machiavellianism has a negative correlation with organizational, supervisor, and team dedication and a good correlation with self-related career commitment. Making financial success the main objective of a firm is positively correlated with Machiavellianism (McHoskey, 1995).

Machiavellian characteristics enable better sales success, according to Aziz et al. (2002). However, as this conclusion in Table 4 makes clear, Machiavellians are destructive leaders who manipulate, mislead, take advantage of others, and only think about themselves (Spain et al., 2014). Their personality traits also significantly impact unproductive job behavior.

According to our study, Machiavellians outperform narcissists and psychopaths in the workplace. This could be because people with high levels of Machiavellianism prioritize their own financial interests and goals over the organization's overall objectives. They may do this by backstabbing, using others as leverage to further their careers, or even firing coworkers for personal gain (LeBreton et al., 2018). They overlook others because they are so driven to achieve their own goal.

The acquisition of Machiavellian views and tactics is likely facilitated through social learning and reinforced by attachment figures, as well as exposure to adverse environmental conditions, such as trauma, harshness, and neglect (Kraut & Price, 1976; Láng & Birkás, 2014; Láng & Lénárd, 2015; McIlwain, 2011). To further elucidate the complexities of Dark Triad personalities, future research should endeavor to investigate these traits across diverse cultural

contexts, exploring the specific factors that motivate individuals personally and professionally. Pakistan presents a unique cultural landscape that warrants examination of the interplay between Dark Triad traits, cultural influences, intelligence, and motivational factors.

Implications

The present study's findings have far-reaching implications for organizations, businesses, and mental health professionals. Notably, this research offers actionable insights for organizations seeking to better comprehend and manage employees exhibiting Dark Triad personality traits, specifically Machiavellianism, Narcissism, and Psychopathy. By gaining a deeper understanding of the characteristic tendencies and behaviors associated with these traits, organizations can refine their recruitment processes, incorporating targeted screening measures to identify potential Dark Triad traits during the initial hiring stages.

Furthermore, the findings of this study can inform the design of targeted interventions aimed at optimizing the job performance and job crafting capabilities of employees exhibiting Dark Triad traits. By recognizing the unique strengths and weaknesses of these individuals, organizations can develop personalized training programs, coaching strategies, and developmental initiatives to help them leverage their talents and overcome limitations, ultimately enhancing their overall job performance and career success.

The findings of this study challenge the prevailing notion that Machiavellian individuals are inherently detrimental to organizational success. Instead, this research suggests that Machiavellians can be valuable assets to organizations, as their personal success is inextricably linked to the organization's success. According to Lesley Clack (2021), employee engagement plays a pivotal role in driving organizational success. Similarly, research emphasizes that an organization's success is inextricably linked to the performance of its employees, underscoring the critical impact of employee productivity on overall organizational outcomes. This nuanced understanding has significant implications for organizational management and leadership.

The present study's findings have profound implications for the fields of psychology and mental health, offering a foundational framework for psychologists and mental health practitioners to develop a nuanced understanding of individuals exhibiting Dark Triad traits. By acknowledging the distinctive strengths and vulnerabilities of these individuals, practitioners can craft tailored therapeutic approaches that foster personal and professional growth, ultimately enriching their overall well-being and quality of life. Furthermore, this study highlights the critical importance of considering cultural and contextual factors that shape the expression and impact of Dark Triad personality traits. By adopting a collaborative and culturally sensitive approach, organizations, businesses, and mental health practitioners can jointly develop effective support systems and interventions that promote the well-being and success of individuals with Dark Triad traits.

This study highlights the importance of considering cultural nuances when assessing the impact of personality traits on job performance. To advance our understanding of Dark Triad traits, future research should explore each trait independently, employing diverse methodologies and incorporating a broader range of variables. Potential avenues include examining relationships between Dark Triad traits and cultural factors, socio-economic status, leadership styles, parenting styles, and organizational outcomes. Additionally, qualitative methods can provide a deeper understanding of Machiavellian individuals' motivations and behaviors. Future studies should also investigate the consequences of promoting Machiavellianism in the workplace, including its impact on employee well-being and organizational citizenship behavior. Moreover, researchers should explore the motivational factors driving Machiavellians' performance, as well as the relationship between Dark Triad traits and leadership styles. By addressing these gaps, researchers and practitioners can develop more effective strategies for managing and developing employees in the Pakistani context, ultimately creating more effective talent management systems that cater to unique employee needs and characteristics.

Limitations

This study has three primary limitations. Firstly, the diverse sample composition, spanning various sectors and hierarchical levels, may have obscured nuanced differences that could have emerged from a more targeted approach. Specifically, the sample included individuals from disparate levels, such as low-level employees, supervisors, leaders, and workers. This heterogeneity, while providing a broad perspective, may have diluted the findings. A more focused study concentrating on a specific group, such as leaders, supervisors, or low-level managers, could have yielded more precise information and deeper insights into the dynamics within that context.

Secondly, the brevity of the Dark Triad personality scale, with only four questions per subscale, may have restricted the depth of information captured for each trait. Employing a more comprehensive scale could have provided richer insights and more accurate results.

Thirdly, the geographical constraint of the sample, limited to Islamabad's population, undermines the generalizability of the findings to other regions of Pakistan. A more diverse sample, representative of various areas across Pakistan, would have enhanced the study's external validity and provided a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between Dark Triad traits, motivation, and job outcomes within the Pakistani context.

Conclusion

This quantitative study investigated the role of Dark Triad personality traits, comprising Narcissism, Machiavellianism, and Psychopathy, in influencing work performance of employees, with motivation as a mediating variable. Using a cross-sectional approach, the study employed regression, mediation, and correlational analyses to examine the relationships between these variables. The results revealed that Narcissism and Machiavellianism were significant predictors of work performance. Moreover, gender did not have any significant influence over these traits, but gender was a significant predictor of motivation, and work performance. These findings suggest that Machiavellianism plays a crucial role in shaping employee behavior and outcomes, highlighting the importance of considering this trait in organizational settings.

Overall, this study contributes to our understanding of the complex relationships between Dark Triad traits, motivation, and job outcomes such as work performance, providing valuable insights for researchers and practitioners alike.

Declaration

Ethical guidelines were rigorously adhered to, including obtaining approval from the Department of Psychology and the Human Research and Ethics Committee at SZABIST. Informed consent was obtained to ensure that participants fully understood the purpose, risks, and benefits of the study before voluntarily agreeing to participate, emphasizing their autonomy. Privacy and confidentiality of participants were maintained, data security was upheld, and debriefing sessions, as detailed in the ethical considerations section, were provided.

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